

**The Alkaloids of *Holarrhena Antidysenterica*. Part II.
Two further New Alkaloids from the Bark and
the Seeds of Indian *Holarrhena* and their
Constitutional Relationship to Conessine.**

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In collaboration with P. P. Pillay, the author communicated in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 553) the isolation of one non-oxygenous and two oxygenous new bases from the bark of Indian *Holarrhena* and characterised them in some detail. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of two further new alkaloids, named *isoconessimine* ($C_{23}H_{38}N_2$) and *conimine* ($C_{22}H_{36}N_2$), initially from the seeds and subsequently from a fresh working of the bark of Indian *Holarrhena*. It further embodies the results of investigation into the relationship of the non-oxygenous bases to conessine.

Out of the three new bases from the bark communicated in Part I (*loc. cit.*) only holarrhimine and conessimine could so far be isolated from the seeds. The yields of the new bases approximately amounted to 0.02 %, but as their complete purification entailed an enormous loss of material, the actual quantities of the bases present in the plant are likely to be far in excess of these yields. The nomenclature of the secondary bases is intended to mark their relationship to conessine and is based on the assumption that the difference between conessimine and *isoconessimine* depends on whether the active H is attached to the one or the other of the two basic nitrogen atoms, and that in conimine one active H is attached to each of the two nitrogen atoms. This assumption is fairly justified by the results of methylation of the secondary bases but a fuller investigation into the problem is in progress.

The isolation of these alkaloids was based on the differences of their basic strength and the separation of the secondary bases as petroleum ether insoluble carbonates. Thus the more strongly basic dissecondary base conimine is precipitated as a carbonate on passing carbon dioxide through a moist ethyl acetate solution of the secondary bases, while conessimine and isoconessimine remain in solution and are separated from each other by means of fractional crystallisation from ethyl acetate, in which isoconessimine is more soluble than conessimine. The main portion of isoconessimine, however, was isolated out of the fraction of tertiary bases from the final mother liquors of conessine hydrogen oxalate, by fractionally precipitating the bases from the aqueous solution of the crystalline hydrobromide with ammonia and caustic soda. Of the three fractions finally obtained by this process, the middle fraction crystallised almost completely from acetone, yielding a base melting at 85°. On repeated fractional crystallisation of this base from petroleum ether and acetone, the middle fraction finally yielded isoconessimine which melted at 92° and gave a large depression in its melting point on admixture with conessimine.

In view of the isolation of three crystalline bases from the mother liquors of conessine hydrogen oxalate by the above mentioned process (from the seeds), it becomes rather doubtful, if Haworth's norconessine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 631), which was isolated from a corresponding fraction of the alkaloids from the seeds and form an uncrystallisable liquid in spite of the high molecular formula $C_{23}H_{38}N_2$, could be rightly considered as a uniform product, particularly when the base from the oxalate was not subjected to a fractional distillation. Haworth himself states that it was not possible to get pure conessine oxalate merely by fractional crystallisation and it is open to doubt, if what was not possible in case of conessine oxalate was so in case of norconessine oxalate.

The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives of conessimine were prepared as additional proofs of its secondary character, already indicated by its forming a nitroso derivative (*loc. cit.*). Its methylation to a ditertiary base presented special difficulty as the methyl iodide in various solvents and under varying conditions invariably added itself on to the tertiary N, yielding a product which combines in itself the characters of a secondary base and a quaternary methiodide. Thus it gave an unstable nitroso derivative and picrate, but the

base could not be liberated from its aqueous solution by caustic soda.

Failing this method of methylation, refluxing the base for a couple of hours with one mol. each of formic acid and formaldehyde at 100° was tried with success. The methyl base was obtained in a yield of 70% of theory, but rather against expectations it melted higher than conessimine and was proved to be conessine by the determination of the mixed melting point and optical activity. Following up this method of methylation both isoconessimine and conimine gave conessine in nearly theoretical yields, and the mixture of the petroleum ether soluble bases (from 2 kg. of the bark), left after the separation of conessine, gave on direct methylation a further yield of 0.4% conessine, the total yield of the base thus amounting to 0.8%

Nearly all the previous authors who have worked on conessine have noted that it forms a red solution on heating in solvents and have recommended as little heating as possible to avoid loss in the yield of the pure base. A certain amount of heating, however, is unavoidable in the process of isolation and it was found that the reddening of solution is reduced to a minimum if the solvents are distilled off in a current of carbon dioxide. In contrast to conessine the solutions of the corresponding secondary bases are much less inclined to turn red on heating. This observation is of interest, as a similar behaviour has been noted before in respect of the corresponding secondary and tertiary bases. Thus nicotine turns dark on standing while *nor*nicotine is fairly stable (Braun and Weissbach, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2018). Also methyl anabasine is less stable than the corresponding *nor*-base anabasine (Orechoff and Norkino, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 725).

At the close of the present investigations, Bertho, Schukmann and Schönberger, (*Ber.*, 1933, 66, 786) recorded the isolation of three new bases from the kurchi bark, namely conessidine ($C_{21}H_{32}N_2$), m. p. 123° conkurchine ($C_{20}H_{32}N_2$), m. p. 153° and kurchenine ($C_{21}H_{32}O_2N_2$), m. p. $335-36^{\circ}$. In view of the number of their carbon atoms and *N*-methyl groups, as well as their melting points and optical activity (*vide* Table), isoconessimine and conimine are quite distinct from conessidine and conkurchine, which may possibly be isolated later from the final mother liquors, which are under investigation.

Table showing the non-oxygenous bases from the bark and the seeds of *Holarrhena antidysenterica*.

Alkaloid.	Formula.	M. p.	$[\alpha]_D$.	No. of N-CH ₃ groups.	Active H after Zerevitinoff.	Author.
Kurchine	C ₂₃ H ₃₈ N ₂	75°	+ 6.4° in absolute alcohol, - 7.57° in chloroform	Not mentioned	...	Ghosh & Ghosh
norConessine	C ₂₃ H ₃₈ N ₂	liquid	+ 6.7°	3	...	Haworth
Conessine	C ₂₄ H ₄₀ N ₂	126°	+ 27.6° in absolute alcohol	3	...	As purified by Siddiqui and Pillay
Conessimine	C ₂₃ H ₃₈ N ₂	100°	- 22.5°	2	1	Siddiqui & Pillay
isoConessimine	C ₂₃ H ₃₈ N ₂	92°	+ 30°	2	1	Present author
Conimine	C ₂₂ H ₃₆ N ₂	134°	- 30°	1	2	„ „
Conessidine	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ N ₂	123°	- 52.2° in chloroform	1	Not mentioned	Bertho, Schuckmann, & Schönberger
Conkurchine	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ N ₂	153°	- 67.4° in 96 % alcohol	0	Do	„

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of the bases from the seeds.—The well powdered seeds (20 kg.) were macerated with a mixture of alcohol and concentrated ammonia (9:1) and then heated to boiling for about ½ hour. After the temperature has come down to about 40°, 10% alcoholic potash was added and well stirred and the first percolate drawn out after a week. Six further percolations were subsequently made with cold 5% alcoholic potash and the combined percolates acidified with acetic acid and freed of the solvent in *vacuo* below 40°. The pasty greenish brown residue was extracted with light petroleum till free from the oil, then made strongly alkaline with caustic soda and extracted with ether and finally chloroform. The ether and chloroform extracts yielded, through the hydrochloride, 130 g. of the total alkaloid as a light reddish yellow treacle. Working on the basis

of the method outlined in the introduction, 40 g. of conessine melting at 123-24° and 2.5 g. of isoconessimine m.p. 92°, were obtained from the non-carbonate-forming fraction, while conimine, m.p. 134° and 2 g. of isoconessimine m. p. 80-90° were obtained from the carbonate-forming fraction, after separating from the later the insoluble sulphates, which yielded 3 g. of holarrhimine, m. p. 183°, after the method given for its isolation in Part I. (*loc. cit.*)

Isolation of the bases from the bark.—Working up 30 kg. of freshly collected, dried bark after the method given in the last communication (*loc. cit.*) and using the process of separation of alkaloids worked out on the seeds, conessine (100 g., m.p. 123-24° and 20 g. second crop, m. p. 120-21°, total yield, 0.4 %), and isoconessimine (2 g.) were obtained from the non-carbonate fraction and conessimine (15 g., 0.05 %), isoconessimine (10 g., 0.03%) and conimine (3 g., 0.01%) from the carbonate fraction. The sulphate group yielded 0.1 % of holarrhimine, traces of holarrhine, and the crystalline residual alkaloid from the mother liquors of holarrhimine, which slowly melt from 150° to 173° (yield 0.05 %). The melting points of the different bases from the bark were identical with those of the corresponding bases from the seeds, the respective mixed m. p. showing no depression. The values of the optical activity of the corresponding bases were also identical within limits of error.

Characterisation of Alkaloids, their Salts and Derivatives.

isoConessimine.

isoConessimine crystallises from its concentrated solutions in petroleum ether or more easily from acetone in puffs of white needles or clusters of well formed broad needles, which in contrast to conessine do not change into plates on stirring. It melts at 92° (corr.) and its solubility in acetone is distinctly greater than that of conessine. It is readily soluble in all the other common organic solvents. In 1.00% solution in absolute alcohol it showed a rotation $\alpha_D^{25} = +30.0^\circ$. (Found: C, 80.4, H, 11.1; N, 8.1. $C_{23}H_{38}N_2$ requires C, 80.7; H, 11.1; N, 8.2 per cent). After Herzig and Meyer's method it showed the presence of 2 *N*-methyls. [Found: CH_3 , 9.5. $C_{23}H_{38}N_2$ requires (for 2 *N*- CH_3) CH_3 , 8.8 per cent].

After Zerevitinoff it showed the presence of 1 active H. [Found: H, 0.22; $C_{23}H_{38}N_2$ requires (for 1 active H), H, 0.29 %]. On

crystallisation from moist ethyl acetate the dihydrate of the base was obtained in aggregates of needles melting at 88.92° . (Found in air dried substance: C, 72.6; H, 11.1. $C_{23}H_{38}N_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires C, 72.0; H, 11.1 per cent). *isoConessimine* forms a carbonate on passing a vigorous current of moist CO_2 through its petroleum ether solution, but the carbonate is much less stable than either *conessimine* or *conimine* carbonate, and forms a sticky semi-solid mass. On exposure to air *isoconessimine* absorbs moisture and CO_2 from the atmosphere and then melts from 80 to 85° , but the original melting point is restored on complete drying in vacuum over chloroform. A similar behaviour has also been noted in case of *conessimine*.

isoConessimine hydrochloride was prepared by bringing together the components in ethereal solution and crystallised from a little alcohol and acetone. It forms a white crystalline powder, m. p. 335° and is exceedingly soluble in alcohol and water. (Found: Cl, 16.9. $C_{23}H_{38}N_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 17.1 per cent).

isoConessimine chloroplatinate, prepared by adding 5% platinum chloride solution to an aqueous solution of *conedine* hydrochloride, formed a dull orange coloured semi-crystalline powder, which begins to darken at 270° , melts with decomposition at 285° and is insoluble in alcohol and water. (Found: Pt, 26.0. $C_{23}H_{38}N_2 \cdot 2HCl \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 25.9 per cent).

isoConessimine hydroiodide was obtained by adding potassium iodide solution to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride as long white needles, melting at 316° . In contrast to the hydroiodide of *conessimine* and its *nor*-bases, *conedine* hydroiodide is quite readily soluble in cold water.

isoConessimine picrate was obtained by adding an aqueous solution of picric acid to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride. It forms clusters of lemon yellow rectangular plates and broad needles from dilute alcohol which give off water at 110° , shrink down at 160° and melt with decomposition at $198-200^{\circ}$. It is difficulty soluble in hot alcohol and water.

isoConessimine hydrobromide was prepared by adding an excess of potassium bromide to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride. It separates out in long silky needles and planks, which are very soluble in water and a little less so in alcohol, m.p. 344° (decomp.).

Methyl isoconessimine: Conessine.—0.28 G. of *isoconessimine* was refluxed on the water-bath for an hour with 1.2 mols. each of formaldehyde (40 % solution) and formic acid (25 % solution). On

working up the reaction product as in case of the conessimine 0.18 g. (60 % of theory) of conessine (m.p. 125°) was obtained. (Found: C, 80.75; H, 11.27; N, 7.87. $C_{24}H_{40}N_2$ requires C, 80.99; H, 11.3; N, 7.87 per cent).

Conimine.

Conimine crystallises from its fairly concentrated solution in ether, petroleum ether, ethyl acetate or acetone in clusters and stars of needles, m.p. 130° (corr.). It is comparatively less soluble in all these solvents than conessimine. Its rotation in 1% absolute alcoholic solution was $\alpha_D^{25} = -30^\circ$. (Found: C, 79.9; H, 11.0; N, 8.7. $C_{22}H_{36}N_2$ requires C, 80.5; H, 11.0; N, 8.5 per cent). It crystallises from moist ethyl acetate as a hydrate, m.p. 130°. (Found: H_2O , 9.9. $C_{22}H_{36}N_2, 2 H_2O$ requires H_2O , 9.89 per cent). The dehydrated base showed the presence of two active H after the method of Zerevitinoff. [Found: H, 0.545. $C_{22}H_{36}N_2$ requires (for 2 active H) H, 0.609 per cent] and of only one $N-CH_3$, after the method of Herzig and Meyer. [Found: CH_3 , 5.1. $C_{22}H_{36}N_2$ requires (for 1 $N-CH_3$) CH_3 , 4.6 per cent].

Conimine hydrochloride was obtained by adding ethereal HCl to an ethereal solution of the base. Crystallised from a little methyl alcohol and acetone it forms nearly colourless aggregates of needles, m.p. 318-20° (decomp.) and is easily soluble in alcohol and water.

Conimine chloroplatinate was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of 5% platinum chloride to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride. It forms a light orange coloured powder, m.p. 296-98° (decomp.) and is very sparingly soluble in hot alcohol or water. (Found: Pt, 26.36, 26.58. $C_{22}H_{36}N_2, 2 HCl, PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 26.47 per cent).

Conimine picrate was prepared by adding aqueous picric acid to the aqueous solution of the base in dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallising the semisolid precipitate from hot water, when it forms clusters of brilliant yellow prismatic rods, which shrink at 134° and melt at 140-41°. It is very sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and water.

Conimine hydroiodide was obtained by adding a concentrated solution of potassium iodide to a solution of the base in dilute hydrochloric acid as a semi-solid precipitate which soon turns crystalline. It crystallises from water in white prismatic rods, m.p. 293°. It is fairly soluble in alcohol, less soluble in water.

Dimethylconimine : Conessine.—On refluxing 1 g. of conimine with 2.2 mol. each of 40 % formaldehyde and formic acid (25%) at 100° for 2 hours and working up the resultant product as in the case of conessimine, 0.07 g. of conessine was obtained (yield 66%). It melted at 125-26° and gave no depression of the melting point on admixture with pure conessine.

Conessimine.

Benzoyl conessimine.—On adding an ethereal solution of benzoyl chloride to an ethereal solution of the base benzoyl conessimine hydrochloride was obtained in nearly theoretical yield as a white crystalline powder which began to soften at 233°, melted at 348° (decomp.) and was easily soluble in water. The base from the hydrochloride was treated with moist carbon dioxide in petroleum ether solution to remove any traces of the unreacted secondary base, dried over potassium carbonate and taken up after removal of the solvent in a little acetone, from which it crystallised in elongated prismatic plates, which shrink at 110°, soften at 115° and melt completely at 121°. (Found: C, 79.4; H, 9.6. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5$ requires C, 80.2; H, 9.8 per cent).

Acetyl conessimine, prepared with acetyl chloride in exactly the same manner as the benzoyl base, formed a pale yellow uncrystallisable treacle. The hydrochloride of the base, as obtained directly from conessimine and acetyl chloride or prepared from the treacly acetyl base, had exactly the same m.p. 278-80° and was easily soluble in alcohol and water. (Found: Cl, 9.4. $C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_3, HCl$ requires Cl, 8.6 per cent).

The chloroplatinate of the acetylated base, obtained by adding an aqueous solution of platonic chloride to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride, formed a buff coloured powder which shrinks with darkening at 230° and melts at 254-56° (decomp.). The platinum value found for it indicates a double salt of the type $(B, HCl) 1\frac{1}{2} PtCl_4$. [Found: Pt, 20.6, 20.8. $(C_{23}H_{37}N_2 \cdot CO \cdot CH_3, HCl), 1\frac{1}{2} PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 20.2 per cent].

Methyl conessimine : Conessine.—0.85 G of the base was refluxed at 100° for 3 hours with 1.2 mol. each of formaldehyde (40%) and formic acid (25%) till the carbon dioxide evolution was completely stopped. The base from the reaction mixture was treated with moist carbon dioxide in petroleum ether solution to remove traces of un-

reacted base and dried over potassium carbonate. On removing the solvent from the filtrate and crystallising the residue from acetone, 0.3 g. of crystals, m.p. 123-24° and further 0.3 g. melting at 121-22° were obtained. The base melting at 123-24° melted at 125-26° on admixture with pure conessine of m.p. 126° and showed a rotation in 2.016 % solution in absolute alcohol, $\alpha_D^{25} = +25.3^\circ$ as against +27.6° noted by the author for pure conessine.

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